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“LIKE AN UNPOLISHED PIECE OF WOOD!”

APPLYING DESIGN SEMIOTICS TO THE ANALYSIS OF VERBALISATIONS OF HAPTIC PRODUCT EXPERIENCES

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents an elaborated analysis of people’s explanations of their haptic product experiences, applying a design semiotic approach, i.e. the relation between a sign signifying something (an object), which is interpreted by someone (an interpretant), who is him/herself part of a sign relation. Conclusions are drawn as to the feasibility of using semiotics, and Peirce’s triad, as a framework for further knowledge and understanding of product experiences in general and haptic product experiences in particular.

Keywords: haptics, design semiotics, product experiences

DESIGN CARRIES MEANINGS

The word design originates from the Latin ‘designare’ which means to mark out, designate, and denote (Etymological Dictionary of the English Language 1988). Design can also be described as communication in that the designer communicates by means of the product. Through the product’s Gestalt, i.e. the totality of colour, material, surface, structure, taste, sound etc. appearing and functioning as a whole, the product communicates a message which is received and interpreted by the receiver, e.g. the customer or user (Monö 1997). What is seen, heard and felt tells someone something, i.e. carries a meaning.

DESIGN SEMIOTICS

Design semiotics have been used in order to analyse the meaning of design artefacts and the way in which products construct meaning (e.g.

Vihma 1995; Wikström 2002, 2006, Karlsson & Wikström 2009).

Signs are used in many different contexts and semiotic theories have been applied within several fields of research, especially in the cultural and linguistic sciences, but also in other areas such as art, architecture, music and film (Nöth 1990). Within semiotics, models and concepts described by Ferdinand de Saussure, Charles Sanders Peirce, and Charles William Morris form the basis for modern design semiotic theory.

Semiotics is the study of sign processes - or semiosis. Semiosis, a term coined by Peirce, was defined by Charles Morris as a sign process, i.e. a process in which something is a sign to some organism (Morris 1946:366 in Nöth 1990). Morris derived tree dyadic relations of semiosis which he considered to be the basis of three dimensions of semiosis and semiotics. *Syntactics* is the study of the relation between a given sign vehicle and other sign vehicles, *semantics* study the relations between sign vehicles and their designate while *pragmatics* study the relation between sign vehicles and their interpreters (Nöth 1990).

According to Charles Sanders Peirce (1931-58, 2.228) “A sign is something which stands to somebody for something in some respect or capacity”. It consists of a relation between three components: representamen (R), object (O) and interpretant (I), in which each unit has a close relationship to each of the others. The form taken by the sign functions as a sign - *representamen* - and refers to something apart from itself, which is what the sign stands for - the *object* - and is

understood or interpreted by someone, i.e., it acquires a meaning or implication in the receiver's consciousness - the *interpretant*. The interpretant is not the sign's user but what Peirce calls "the actual significant effect" (ibid.), i.e. the mental conception that is created by both the represented form and the user's experience of the object, as a consequence of the interpretation. The representamen may be a physical thing, a word for the thing, or a mental image of the thing. The object may be another thing, a metaphor, an activity, a function, an event, a quality, or a property.

The individual interprets the relationship between representamen (R) and object (O). This relationship then forms semantic consequences in terms of recognition, emotions, evaluations, conceptions, impulses to act, understanding etc. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The triad.

For example a chair, i.e. a physical thing or product (representamen), refers to sitting (object). A chair affords an action independently of whether you intend to sit on the chair or not. The chair refers also to properties such as robust and comfortable (object). This relationship (R+O) forms semantic consequences in terms of an impulse to sit or an emotion, such as feeling relaxed in the chair (interpretant). By studying various reference relations, one can describe the product, analyze its qualities and argue its meanings (Vihma 1995; Wikström 2002, 2006).

Design semiotics could be seen as a process of abstraction, where concrete objects are viewed as signs that are capable of producing meaning when placed in combinations and constellations. Building on Peirce, Vihma (1995) argues that the physical product can be manifested in the object, or in the representamen, or in the relationship between these two parts of the triad.

Peirce divides signs into three sign categories: icon, index and symbol, where each category displays a different relationship between the representamen (R) and the object (O), i.e., how R refers to O (Nöth 1990).

The *icon* is a category of signs that builds upon similarity between physical form and what it refers to, such as another product, an activity, or a property or expression. Metaphors can be regarded as icons (Vihma 1995) and a metaphor may be used to give a product some specific expression. A product may express characteristics that resemble those of another product and their relationship can then be called metaphorical. For example, a sports car expressing speed and efficiency could be used as a metaphor for creating these expressions in, e.g., a vacuum cleaner.

The *index* builds upon closeness or a causal connection between the representamen and the object. A represented form may refer to usage (Vihma 1995), e.g., a doorknob can describe the way it should be gripped and turned.

A *symbol*, finally, means something because of an agreement between people. It is a mental and social construction that builds upon learning. Examples of symbols are various types of graphic signs.

SENSORY DESIGN

Even though all human senses are regarded as important, the visual sense is most often regarded as the dominant one and has been studied extensively in different sciences (e.g. Paterson, 2007). It is also the sense that has been investigated the most in the context of product

development and design even though the importance of considering several senses have been strongly argued in order to e.g. grasp how people recognize an item (Newell et al, 2001), how they form a percept of a product (Ernst and Bühlhoff, 2004), and how they experience their interaction with and use of products (Monö 1997). It has further been claimed that different modalities convey different types of information to the individual, information that is compared, combined, integrated and finally processed to form a coherent understanding of the item or thing that is perceived (Ludden, 2008). Hence, it can be argued that the meaning of the design artefact is constructed on the basis of impressions received from several senses. Nevertheless, most often the visual aspects of the physical artefact have been the main focus for design analysis, also for semiotic analyses of meaning (e.g. Wihma, 1995; Wikström, 2002; Opperud, 2004) while e.g. haptic aspects have not (to the authors' knowledge) been approached in the same way.

UNDERSTANDING HAPTIC PRODUCT EXPERIENCES

INTRODUCTION

Haptics can be described as the active sense of touch and involve everything that can be perceived by sensorial receptors in the skin, muscles, joints and tendons. When people explore and interact with products, such as when touching a surface, lifting something or pressing a button, they obtain haptic impressions which send signals to the brain. The haptically perceived properties of a product, such as its weight, form, stiffness etc., combine to convey an overall impression of the product.

THE EMPIRICAL BASIS

Study I

A series of studies has been carried out in order to develop further knowledge on the relationship between haptic product properties and people's haptic experiences. In a recent study (Dagman et al. 2010a) was concluded that haptic product experiences involve different so called experience

dimensions (EDs). Based on the EDs the experiences can be categorized according to five different dimensions: "objective/measurable", "evaluative/aesthetic", "emotional", "social status/position" and "interface qualities" - the categorization based upon a linguistic classification of adjectives proposed by Krippendorff (2005). Furthermore, the study proposed that product experiences seem related to a few, fundamental haptically perceivable product properties.

Study II

In a second study the effects of three such fundamental 'haptic properties' on people's haptic experiences were investigated (Dagman, 2010). Altogether participated 36 individuals, 14 men and 22 women. Their ages ranged from 20 to 60 years (mean=40.8), the upper age limit due to sensitivity of the skin decreasing as one grows older (Harding, 2004). The participants were allowed to haptically explore six different physical items, one by one, by hand behind curtains. No visual contact was allowed.

The properties investigated were shape, weight, and surface structure, the selection based on Klatzky's and Lederman's (2003) categorization of haptic properties in terms of geometric and material properties. The geometric property chosen was shape and the material property was surface structure. The third property, weight, is a combination of material and geometric properties (ibid.). The three were then varied in three different ways, i.e. three different shapes, three different surface textures, and three different resulting in altogether 27 combinations.

Figure 2: The three different shapes of the items

The specific shapes were decided upon based on the following criteria: the shapes should be possible to be grasped with one hand, the volumes should be as similar as possible, and the shapes should be familiar, basic shapes. The final selection was inspired by Biederman's (1985; 1987) set of basic geometrical ions, or *geons* (see Figure 2 and Table 1). According to Biederman a complex object can be decomposed into predefined elementary objects called *geons*.

The differences in weights were to be large enough so that one object could easily be distinguished from the other in terms of its weight. At the same time the objects were not to be too heavy to be manually explored for a couple of minutes. Also material and manufacturing limits also affected the possible weights. The final weights 0.150 kg, 0.260 kg and 0.5 kg.

The different surface textures were accomplished by different surface treatments (see Table 1). The final results were characterized as "smooth", "sticky" and "coarse". The differences were large enough in order that the different surfaces could be clearly discriminated.

Table 1: A description of the different surfaces.

Description	Association	Surface treatment	Specification
Smooth	Soap	A 2-component semi-matt lacquer	DM 394-0018 Bernyl Deluc 18
Sticky	Leather	A coating of stone chip protection spray	Henkel Teroson GmbH D-69112 Heidelberg Germany
Coarse	Fine sanding paper	A matt lacquer producing a slightly abrasive character to the surface	Hagman black matt aerosol, nr 11490

Information on the participants' experiences was collected by means of a questionnaire (a semantic differential, bipolar adjective pairs, 7-step scale). The selection of adjectives were based on three criteria: (i) they had been identified as frequently used adjectives to describe haptic experiences (see study I described in Dagman 2010), (ii) they were considered suitable for the items chosen for the study and (iii) they represented four of five EDs: "Objective and Measurable", "Emotional",

"Aesthetic and Evaluative" and "Interface qualities" (see Table 2). The fifth ED, "Social status and positions", was excluded since it includes adjectives that are very contextual to its nature.

The participants were also asked to provide explanations to their responses immediately after each assessment. The verbal data were recorded, the transcripts analyzed and the results organised according to the experience dimensions.

Table 2: The selected adjective-pairs organised in relation to the Experience Dimensions (EDs).

Experience Dimension (ED)	The adjectives
Objective/measurable	1. Robust/Fragile
	2. Rough/Smooth
	3. Hard/Soft
	4. Stale/Unstable
	5. Cold/Warm
	6. Gainly/Ungainly
	7. Heavy/Light
	8. Big/Small
Evaluative/aesthetic	9. Balanced/Unbalanced
	10. Simple/Complicated
Emotional	11. Happy/Mournful
	12. Exciting/Boring
	13. Unpleasant/Pleasant
Interface qualities	14. Graspable/Ungraspable

AIM

The aim of this paper is to address the feasibility of applying a design semiotic approach to analysing people's verbalisations of haptic product experiences, and hereby reach a deeper understanding of what aspects contribute to product experiences, including the attribution of meaning in general and haptic product experience in particular.

The physical item explored in the empirical study were not products. However, shapes (such as cube, cylinder and prism shapes) are typically used as bases for creating product form, as are weight and surface structure used in order to create different qualities.

The first question posed was if meanings were created even though the items were not actual products? The second question was if meanings were created, what were these meanings?

METHOD

The empirical data was collected in Study II (Dagman 2010) as described in “Empirical basis”. According to the results of the study shape had a statistical significant effect on all EDs while surface and weight had a significant effect only on one ED, “objective/measurable”. Furthermore, shape had a statistically significant effect on the experiences related to the following pairs of adjectives in the semantic instrument: gainly-ungainly, simple-complicated, exciting-boring, pleasant-unpleasant, and graspable-ungraspable (Figure 3). Shape was therefore chosen as the focus for the further analysis even though also weight and surface had an impact on the assessments.

Peirce’s semiotic theory and triadic sign model, i.e. representamen (R), object (O) and interpretant (I), and the three sign categories, i.e. icon, index and symbol, provided the basis for the semiotic analysis. The same approach has earlier been successfully used to analyze visual experiences of product form (Wikström, 2002; Opperud, 2004; Karlsson and Wikström, 2009) and has shown potential in developing in-depth understanding of a participant’s thinking when creating an impression of a product, i.e. the connection between the concrete/tangible perceptive aspects of the product and the participant’s product experience can thus be clarified. The participants’ comments and the segments holding meanings were structured according to this triadic model.

RESULTS

The result of the analysis of the participants’ explanations show that the assessments did not occur in a “vacuum”. The participants searched

for a meaning in order to assess the items according to the semantic scale presented. In this process different references were used for verbalising and explaining the haptic experiences: in the specific case shape, material, (another) expression, a metaphor, and an activity.

According to Peirce’s triadic sign model these references can be described as follows. Shape is the haptic experience of the actual, physical form. Material is part of the product gestalt and is of considerable importance in haptic experiences. The shape and the material are representamen, i.e. the physical aspect that works as a concrete sign in the semiosis. Expressions are other qualities or properties that shape and material refer to in relation to the given adjective. Metaphors can be regarded as icons and a metaphor may be used to give a product some specific expression. The product may express characteristics that resemble those of another product, and their relationship can, as indicated earlier, then be called metaphorical. The expression and the metaphor are objects in Peirce’s sign model. Activity is the experience of shape described as a physical interaction or a mental activity. Activity can be referred to as interpretant (interpretant is an ongoing process not to be confused with any individual interpreter.)

The results of the analysis also show that different adjectives triggered different references for the same item, i.e. aspects such as associations and activities. Furthermore, it appears as though the references differed depending upon the type of experience dimension.

Below follows a synthesis of the participants’ explanations of what produced a certain experience in study II in relation to shape, i.e. cubes, cylinders and triangular prisms.

Figure 3: The result of the participant experiences, median values (n=36).

GAINLY-UNGAINLY

The experience of *gainly-ungainly* refers to an experience of gracefulness. The cubes and triangular prisms were as a whole experienced as somewhat ungainly, slightly more so than the cylinders (Figure 3).

The references for the cubes were *representamen*, i.e. the actual, concrete, perception of the item. In this example (Figure 4) the *representamen* is described as "no sharp edges", "doesn't tail away into something", "has a heaviness inside that makes it feel little bulky" (referring to shape) and "it doesn't feel moldable", (it is) wood, plastic (referring to material). In the next step of the semiosis, references are created based upon the *representamen*. These references define the *object* in the semiosis. The cubes created references such as stiff, hard, compact, soft, angular, ungraspable (expression or other properties) and/or referred to another product

which resembled the shape, such as "a big soap" (metaphor). These references were, together with the perceived object, put together by the individual and are defined as the *interpretant*, i.e. the mental process that creates a meaning. The individual interacted with the item and the item received its meaning in terms of an activity expressed as "It is quite difficult to hold it in my hands" and "Not neat in the hand but it can be good for piling" (activity type 1). In the next step the person was mentally moving to another activity based upon previous experiences or conceptions, described as "(It is) difficult to carry in my pocket" (activity type 2). This process explains the assessment of how gainly/ungainly the haptic experience. The differences in the participants' appear to be linked to the specific physical features, i.e. the cylinders with their rounded shape compared to the edges and sharp angles in the cubes and prisms, but not limited to these. The differences appear also in the relation between R-O-I.

The semiotic analysis of the items have followed the same structure and are described in the following.

The references for the cylinders were:

- *Representamen*: "low mass in relation to its size, makes it feel a bit larger" (shape), "cannot be reshaped but is still not bulky" (material).
- *Object*: elastic, heavy but flexible, graspable (expression or other properties), a tube, a table leg (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "you can move it between your hands", "easy to hold in one's hand and

handle with only one hand", "you can roll it", "you can throw it" (activity type 1).

The references for the triangular prisms were:

- *Representamen*: "there are too many edges", "large and stable in one direction" (shape), "cannot be reshaped" (material).
- *Object*: rigid, long, angular, stable (expression or other properties), "a kid's toy", "not shaped as a hour glass" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "large in hand and difficult to handle" (activity type 1), "can build and potter with it in many different ways" (activity type 2).

Figure 4: Representation of the semiotic analyses of the cube shaped items.

GRASPABLE-UNGRASPABLE

Shape had a significant effect also on how *graspable-ungraspable* the items were experienced (Figure 3). Differences were found for the cylinders compared to the cubes and the prism shaped items. The strongest experience of graspable was evoked by the cylinders. The triangular prism shapes was experienced as rather 'neutral', i.e. as neither *graspable nor ungraspable*.

The references for the cubes were:

- *Representamen*: "somewhat too large and angular in its form", "the weight does not feel evenly distributed" (shape), "good friction" (material).

- *Object*: angular, large (expression or other properties), "if it was a hand tool it would not be nice to hold it" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "It feels all right in my hand but in the long run I am not so sure", "not really ergonomic" (activity type1).

The references for the cylinders were:

- *Representamen*: "nothing sharp, cold or strange" (shape), "the surface makes it stuck to your hand" (material).
- *Object*: coarse, steady, smooth, soft (expression or other properties), "like a handrail", "reminds me of a baton" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "it stays in your hand as casted, easy to throw back and forth, my fingers reach all the way around the object" (activity 1).

The references for the triangular prisms were:

- *Representamen*: "large and angular" (shape).
- *Object*: pleasant, steady (expression or other properties), "you can use it as handle", "if you hold it as a bat it is a bit angular", "a block of concrete" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "you can hold it but it is too wide and have too many edges", "as easy as could be to grasp" (activity type 1).

Graspable -ungraspable created hence similar references as did *gainly - ungainly*. The items are e.g. described as "no sharp protrusive edges" and "It feels all right in my hand but in the long run I am not so sure" which is here interpreted as though graspable- ungraspable is partly assessed depending on how gainly or ungainly the experience. Gainly-ungainly evoke references to physical interaction, "large in hand and difficult to handle" but also to a mental activity, "can build and potter with it in many different ways". However, in assessing graspable-ungraspable it appears as though the individual remains in the interaction with the physical item to form the experience. There appears to be no shift to a mental activity

SIMPLE-COMPLICATED

A statistically significant effect of shape was found also for the experience *simple-complicated* (Figure 3). A difference was here found for the triangular prism compared to the cubes and the cylinder shaped objects. The cubes and cylinders were experienced as very simple shapes whereas the triangular prisms were experienced as the least simple of the three, i.e. it was simple "... *but not as a cube or sphere*".

The references for the cubes were:

- *Representamen*: "simple geometry and construction", "uniform size", "no decorations", "can figure out how it feels" (shape), "like an unpolished piece of wood", plastic (material).
- *Object*: very basic, classic, sophisticated, natural, unpretentious, "pure style"

(expression or other properties), "a building brick", "a simple basic toy" (metaphor).

- *Interpretant*: "easy to produce, I can saw it and put it together myself and sand paper" (activity type 2).

The references for the cylinders were:

- *Representamen*: "not tooled in any way", "symmetrical around its axis", "a one piece, just the same shape all the way" (shape), "lacquered or oiled" (material).
- *Object*: ordinary, unpretentious, easy to use, uncomplicated, symmetrical (expression or other properties), "table leg", "coca-cola can", "a kids' toy" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "easy to hold, to move between the hands, " (activity type 1), " a shape like this is easy to produce" (activity type 2).

The references for the triangular prisms were:

- *Representamen*: "no decorations or ornaments or protuberances", "it is a couple of plane surfaces", "a bit more complicated than just a square, different shapes and edges and some more angles" (shape), simple texture, wood (material).
- *Object*: uniform, plane, tooled (expression or other properties).
- *Interpretant*: "I can fast figure out how it feels" (activity type 1), "if it is supposed to be put together with something else, a little extra thinking is required", "a bit more complicated to manufacture", "simple but require some more work if sawing it yourself" (activity type 2).

When assessing the items in relation to *simple-complicated* an item could be described as e.g. "like an unpolished piece of wood", referring to the property "very basic" as well as the metaphor "s simple basic toy". However, the individuals also referred to activities, such as physical interaction and handling such as "move between the hands", and mental activity, "if it is supposed to be put together with something else a little extra thinking is required". In the case of simple-complicated also manufacturing/production aspects became a reference, "easy to produce", "I

can saw it and put it together myself and sandpaper it”.

EXCITING-BORING

The triangular prisms were experienced as the most *exciting* shape. The cylinders were experienced as neither *exciting nor boring* whereas the cubes were experienced as slightly *boring* (Figure 3).

The references for the cubes were:

- *Representamen*: "this shape will not surprise me even if I were looking at it" (shape).
- *Object*: monotonous, uninteresting (expression or other properties), "a building block" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "nothing I would like to have at home, or watch" (activity type 2).

The references for the cylinders were:

- *Representamen*: "a elementary form - nothing exciting about it" (shape), "metallic" (material).
- *Object*: simple, boring (expression or other properties), "could have been something inside - like a container", spilikins (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "you cannot do much with it" (activity type 1).

The references for the prisms:

- *Representamen*: "a bit more unusual, not just basic" (shape), "you wonder what it is... painted wood or concrete?" (material).
- *Object*: funny, happy, different, simple (expression or other properties), "as Salvador Dali - you discover more and more" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "little more to touch" (activity type 1), "there is so much you can do with it" (activity type 2).

Exciting-Boring is the only aspect where the results point in both directions (Figure 3). The cubes were experienced as boring, cylinders as 'neutral' and the triangular prisms as exciting. By structuring the references according to the semiotic analysis these differences can be clarified. The cubes resulted in obvious, boring

references such as "this shape will not surprise me even if I were looking at it" and "nothing I would like to have at home, or watch". The cylinders trigger references which are both exciting ("... a baking roller, you can make bread and cinnamons buns") and boring ("... you cannot do much with it"). The triangular prisms produced positive references and were experienced as exiting: it is unusual, it is different, you find out new things about the item when interacting with it. If one compares the comments re the prisms, the cubes and the cylinders, something "more" appeared to be happening in the prism with its edges and its complexity, which affected the assessment.

UNPLEASANT-PLEASANT

In addition, the triangular prisms provoked a statistically significant difference regarding the experience of *unpleasant-pleasant* in comparison to the cubes and cylinders. The cylinder shape items produced the strongest experience of pleasantness. Also the cubes were experienced as pleasant while the triangular prisms were experienced as both pleasant and unpleasant.

The references for the cubes were:

- *Representamen*: "It is a nice shape, you recognize it and it is just the right size" (shape), "like wood, a little softness" (material).
- *Object*: harmless, uncertain, fun, nice, soft (expression or other properties), "a box" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "you can move it from hand to hand - but nothing you want to hold in your hand for a longer time", "feels good to touch - becomes almost a little anti stressant", "doesn't cause any scary emotions", "nothing you can hurt yourself on" (activity type 1)

The references for the cylinder (pleasant 2) were:

- *Representamen*: "the rounding makes it more pleasant" (shape), coarse, smooth (material).
- *Object*: soft, smooth, solid, confident, cold (expression or other properties), "I associate it with play and children" (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: "there is nothing I can hurt myself on, like sharp edges" (activity type 1),

“one can hit someone on the head with this”
(activity type 2).

The references for the triangular prism (neutral 0) were:

- *Representamen*: “no sharp protrusive edges”, a little more thought behind the shape, can follow a pattern in the geometry” (shape), “it feels like a natural material” (material).
- *Object*: hard, sharp, cold, cunning, pleasant, harmonic (expression or other properties), “according to its shape I associate it with war and something awful”, toy, space (metaphor).
- *Interpretant*: “something that one can hurt oneself on”, “feels good in my hands”, “I have to make an effort to keep it in my hands” (activity 1), “unfinished - too much for me - as those things you did in school and never finished” (activity 2).

Unpleasant-Pleasant is an emotional dimension. The references appear to be created in a similar way as earlier described but a further analysis reveals a clearer focus on emotions specifically. The different shaped items produced positive references as “feels good to touch” and “play and children” but also some negative references as in the case of the cylinder - “one can hit someone on the head with this” or in the case of the prism “war”, “something awful”. Depending upon the references created, the assessment of the experience became pleasant or unpleasant for the individual.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Earlier studies have found that prior knowledge and experience have an impact on users’ perception and assessment of products (e.g. Karana et al., 2009). In addition, a user’s experiences can be expected to differ depending upon whether the product is manipulated only for the purpose of e.g. recognition or it is interacted with in a n actual use activity. The reason for using “nonsense” items rather than actual products in the present study was to be able to study the impact of haptic properties without the participants being biased by previous product experiences and thus by expectations. The

analysis of the verbalised comments demonstrate that the participants nevertheless often made associations to a product or products, or at least to certain functions, and furthermore that these associations played an important role in their assessments and descriptions of their haptic experiences. Thus, the basic shapes appeared to create meanings in the person interacting with them as though they were products with a function. In fact, it appeared as though the items had to have a meaning in order for the participants to be able to relate to the haptic experience, if not for all, at least for several of the experience dimensions.

When assessing product expressions or product experiences most often a quantification of the experience is desired in order e.g. to compare different designs and the impact of e.g. shapes and/or weight and/or surface structures, etc. The results are often, as was the case in study II (Dagman, 2010), represented in terms of mean or median values. Given a median value of “0”, the experience could be judged as “neutral” and the item as, e.g., neither pleasant or unpleasant. Analysing the individual assessments a range, or deviation between individuals, is discovered which could be interpreted as though users perceive different perceptions - or that subjective assessments are not possible as they will always differ). However, based on the semiotic analysis it is evident that initial perception of an object may be the same across individuals but the associations may still move in opposite directions resulting in e.g. an overall pleasant or unpleasant experience. Thus it is not the perception of the item per se that is pleasant-unpleasant but the meanings created in the semiosis.

In study II, a semantic scale was used to quantify the participants’ haptic experiences. The adjectives used for creating the semantic scale played a fundamental role in the semiosis. It appeared as though it was the individuals’ perception of the item and the adjectives that initiated, or triggered, the process. Thus, when addressing people’s experience of artefacts by means of a semantic scale, the adjectives used to

construct the instrument must be chosen with great care. At the same time it can be acknowledged that the adjectives provide an opportunity to support people in eliciting information on their experiences a product, they have a “mediating” function. Furthermore, by creating a semantic scale based on the experience dimensions proposed by Krippendorff (2005) it can be argued that a richer and possibly more complete picture of the individual’s product experience can be obtained than if one would simply ask a participant to describe his or her experiences. However, the methodology applied must allow for and facilitate the process. Providing an instrument, even if open questions for comments of why a certain assessment is given, may not suffice for the process to take place. The participants must be allowed time and be enabled to verbalise that which is here described as a semiotic process, moving from the representamen, to the object, to the interpretant, a process that can be supported by well thought through probing or supporting questions.

The analysis of the empirical data from study II indicates that a design semiotics approach to the analysis of product experiences can be applied to haptic experiences in the same way that it has earlier been used to analyse to visual impression (cf. Wikström 2002, Opperud 2004). The items used in the study created a meaning and Pierce’s model could be used to follow the process in which meanings are created, i.e. the semiosis, and to explain how this meaning is created and what aspects contribute to this creation.

Based on the experiences from the analysis presented in the study, it is here proposed that the design semiotic approach could provide an effective tool for studying users’ experiences of products. The different parts of the semiosis, R, O, I, can be used in order to structure an interview as well as to analyse the information collected. The approach can also be applied when designing a product and its message. Within design semiotics, a thing is focused upon as a sign, along with its ability and possibilities to bear and convey a message. In the field of industrial design, it

is important that the product, through its material form, is given an opportunity to communicate the intended message to a user. If we cannot understand the product’s meaning and/or its function through its design it becomes incomprehensible to us which can have negative consequences in the situation of use. Design semiotics are a conceptual apparatus which makes it possible to analyse, discuss, and formulate requirements for a future product’s meaning. The relation between user and product can then be further analysed and discussed. Knowledge of design semiotics is thus important for the product developing company when creating new products.

In sum, design semiotics provide designers with an effective tool for designing a product and its intended message and a focus on the product’s communicative functions. However, in order to utilise the full potential of the method, the designer must have knowledge of design semiotic theory and experience of how to apply Peirce’s sign model in practical design work.

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